

CHARACTERISTICS OF PERSONAL DIGNITY AND FREEDOM, GENDER EQUALITY

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Abstract. *In recent years, gender and its concepts have become the common focus of social changes and social debates. Many societies, including world society, have seen rapid changes in gender role concepts, media portrayals of gender, and gender-related legal trends. This article reflects on the value and freedom of the individual, the peculiarities of gender equality.*

Keywords: *concept of identity, freedom, gender problem, gender equality, community in the world, research, habit, difference.*

ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ЛИЧНОГО ДОСТОИНСТВА И СВОБОДЫ, ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА

Аннотация. *В последние годы гендер и его концепции стали общим центром социальных изменений и социальных дебатов. Многие общества, в том числе мировое сообщество, стали свидетелями быстрых изменений в концепциях гендерных ролей, представлении гендера в средствах массовой информации и правовых тенденциях, связанных с гендером. В данной статье размышляется о ценности и свободе личности, особенностях гендерного равенства.*

Ключевые слова: *концепция идентичности, свобода, гендерная проблема, гендерное равенство, общность в мире, исследование, привычка, отличие.*

INTRODUCTION

It was not until the first decades of the 20th century that the personality began to be studied by psychologists, who until then were engaged in the study of human conditions and cognitive processes. In the 20th century, as experimental researches in psychology were intensively conducted, mathematical-statistical data calculation was used in order to accurately test hypotheses and obtain grounded facts. On this basis, the development of reliable and valid test methods for the study of proportional personality has been the first priority for psychologists for many years. There are different theories and concepts regarding the classification of personality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Personality maturity is characterized by having physical, mental, political, legal, moral, ecological and aesthetic aspects. These aspects of maturity occur unevenly, that is, at different rates. For example, the physical development of a person is almost the same as it was 50 thousand years ago. However, in the mental maturity of a person, due to the development of thinking, very large positive (forward) shifts have been observed. Pedagogy studies personality development together with all its components.

Known as culture, gender equality, inequality, or problem through behaviors, attitudes, and personality traits defined as male or female. A person's gender identity refers to their psychological sense of being male or female. In contrast, the orientation of a person's emotional and erotic attraction to representatives of the opposite gender, the same gender, or both genders. These are important differences, and although we will not discuss each of these terms in detail, it

should be recognized that they are not always mutually exclusive. A person can be biologically male but have a female identity while being attracted to women, or some other combination of identities and orientations.

It is known that in the early days of independence, our country set the main goal of building a legal democratic state and a just civil society based on a free market economy. In the main link of this, we aim to provide the rights and freedoms of every member of the society as a priority, to create conditions for a free and prosperous life. As the legal basis of this activity, special norms have been included in our constitution. In particular, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: "Democracy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on universal principles, according to which a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inviolable rights are the highest value."

Differences between men and women can be based on: actual gender differences (ie, men and women actually differ in some abilities. Also gender roles (ie, how men and women should act differences and gender stereotypes (that is, how men and women are physically and psychologically different.

RESULTS

Today, psychology explains the personality as a socio-psychological product that is formed in the life of a person in society. When a person, as a social being, enters into relationships with other people, and these relationships become a decisive factor in the formation of his personality, he acquires new qualities.

In foreign psychology, temperament, sensibility, motives, abilities, inclinations, which make up a set of stable characters as a human personality, and spirituality, which determines the flow of thoughts and behavior characteristic of this person when adapting to different life situations, is understood. According to J. Godfrey, personality is generally determined by both genetic and socio-cultural influences. The concept of "personality" includes natural characteristics (gender, temperament, etc.) in the process of active interactions with the social environment (family, school, "significant others") and activities (play, knowledge, work). unites the set of social qualities characteristic of the resulting individual.

The basis of the personality is its structure, which consists in the fact that the personality as a whole product has relatively stable communication and interaction on all sides. Psychologists distinguish different components in the personality structure. S.L. Rubinstein in temperament, character, abilities; in knowledge, skills and abilities; shows the individual-typological features manifested in the direction.

We analyze the nature of needs in order to determine why human actions are activated, but in order to know the consequences of this activity, we need to analyze what determines its direction. Orientation refers to a set of stable motives that guide the individual's activities and are relatively independent of personal circumstances. For example, when the student's behavior is considered as a whole, it is necessary to identify stable motives in the analysis of his psychology. It is only in this case that it is possible to assess the randomness or regularity of the behavior of the teenager, to foresee the possibilities of its repetition, to eliminate some of the personality traits, and to stimulate the development of others. Motives may or may not be conscious to one degree or another. Perceived motives occupy the main place in the direction of the personality. In the modern world, the family has new forms and has been significantly

changed compared to the traditional forms of family relations accepted during previous generations.

DISCUSSION

What are the real gender differences? Regarding language and language skills, girls develop language skills earlier and know more words than boys; but this does not make long-term differences. Girls are also more likely than boys to give compliments, agree with the interviewer, and elaborate on the other person's comments; boys, on the other hand, are more likely to express their opinions and criticize than girls. Boys show higher rates of physical aggression than girls and are more likely to play organized rough games.

Regarding aggression, boys show higher levels of unprovoked physical aggression than girls, but there is no difference in provoked aggression. Some of the big differences involve the children's play styles. Boys often engage in rough and tumble play in large groups, while girls engage in less physical activity in much smaller groups. There are also differences in depression rates, with girls more likely than boys to become depressed after puberty. After puberty, girls are also more dissatisfied with their bodies than boys.

However, there is considerable variability between individual males and individual females. Furthermore, even when there are moderate differences, the actual size of most of these differences is very small. This means that knowing someone's gender is not very helpful in predicting their true characteristics. For example, according to the level of activity, boys are considered more active than girls. Furthermore, many gender differences do not reflect innate differences, but instead reflect differences in specific experiences and socialization. For example, a hypothesized gender difference is that boys demonstrate better spatial abilities than girls.

Many of the grounds on which we differ between the sexes are really based on gender stereotypes and not real differences. Based on the latest analysis, based on the analysis of thousands of studies of more than one million people, studies have shown that: girls are less fearful, shy or afraid of new things than boys; boys are not more angry than girls and girls are not more emotional than boys; boys do not do better in math than girls. One of the theories that explains the formation of gender roles in children is the theory of social learning. Social learning theory states that gender roles are learned through reinforcement, punishment, and modeling. Children are rewarded and reinforced for behaving in accordance with gender roles and punished for violating gender roles. In addition, social learning theory suggests that children learn their gender roles by modeling the behavior of adults and older children, thereby developing ideas about appropriate behavior for each gender.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the gender issue is the reason for the most discussion and controversy today. Society develops further through mutually beneficial cooperation of individuals. Research is being done to solve the gender problem and the psychological basis is very important in this regard. The social learning theory is less supported than the gender schema theory - research shows that parents reinforce gender-appropriate play, but in most cases they treat their male and female children the same. Boy and the different treatment of girls and men and women is both a result of gender difference and a cause of gender difference.

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